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BIOANALYTICAL METHOD DEVELOPMENT AND VALIDATION OF NIRAPARIB IN PLASMA SAMPLES BY LC-MS/MS

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ABSTRACT

In this manuscript, authors developed a simple, sensitive and specific liquid chromatography–tandem mass spectrometry (LC–MS/MS) method was used for quantification of Niraparib in plasma samples. Zorbax SB-C18, 4.6 x 75 mm, 3.5 μm, 80 Å column, 5mM ammonium acetate: methanol (30:70 v/v) mobile phase was used for Chromatographic separation of Niraparib. MRM positive mode was used to detect the Niraparib at 321.5→195.4. Liquid-liquid extraction was employed in the extraction of analytes from human plasma. This method is validated over a linear concentration range of 10.0 – 10000.0 pg/mL with a correlation coefficient (r) of ≥ 0.9997 . The developed method was validated and found to be table in plasma samples.

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INTRODUCTION

Ovarian cancer is the first cause of death from gynaecological malignancy. Germline mutation in BRCA1 and 2, two genes involved in the mechanisms of reparation of DNA damage, are showed to be related with the incidence of breast and ovarian cancer, both sporadic and familiar. PARP is a family of enzymes involved in the base excision repair (BER) system. The introduction of inhibitors of PARP in patients with BRCA-mutated ovarian cancer is correlated with the concept of synthetic lethality^[1-4].

Niraparib (NR) is an inhibitor of poly(ADP-ribose) polymerase (PARP) enzymes, PARP-1 and PARP-2, which play a role in DNA repair. In vitro studies have shown that niraparib-induced cytotoxicity may involve inhibition of PARP enzymatic activity and increased formation of PARP-DNA complexes resulting in DNA damage, apoptosis and cell death. Increased niraparib-induced cytotoxicity was observed in tumor cell lines with or without deficiencies in BRCA1/2. Niraparib decreased tumor growth in mouse xenograft models of human cancer cell lines with deficiencies in BRCA1/2 and in human patient-derived xenograft tumor models with homologous recombination deficiency that had either mutated or wild type BRCA1/2^[5-7].

The chemical name for niraparib tosylate monohydrate is 2-{4-[(3S)-piperidin-3-yl]phenyl}-2Hindazole 7-carboxamide 4-methylbenzenesulfonate hydrate (1:1:1). The molecular formula is C₂₆H₃₀N₄O₅S and it has a molecular weight of 510.61 amu^[8].

Literature survey reveals that only few methods were reported for quantification of Niraparib in human plasma by using LC-MS/MS^[9]. We observed so many difficulties with the reported methods in terms of reproducibility and stability for long run analysis.

It is important to develop the good bio analytical method with proper deuterated or analogue based internal standards interms of matrix effect and reproducibility. The goal of the present study is to develop and validate bioanalytical method to quantify Niraparib in human plasma samples with by LC-MS/MS compare with respective deuterated internal standard as per US-FDA guidelines^[10-12]. Moreover, it has to be developed simple extraction method, with a highly sensitive, good linear method with the small amount of plasma usage. The proposed method is five folds higher sensitive than the reported methods.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Chemicals and reagents

Niraparib (NR) (AbbVie, Inc. (North Chicago, IL), Niraparib-D4 (NRD4) (Champchem, China), diethyl ether, methanol (J.T. Baker USA), Potassium dihydrogen phosphate, ammonium acetate (Merck Limited, Worli, Mumbai). Ultra pure water (Milli-Q system, Millipore, Bedford, MA, USA), Screened human plasma (navjeevan blood bank, Hyderabad, A.P). The chemicals and solvents were used in this study analytical and HPLC grade.

Instrumentation

The 1200 Series HPLC system (Agilent Technologies, Waldbronn, Germany). Mass spectrometric detection was performed on an API 4000 triple quadrupole instrument (ABI-SCIEX, Toronto, Canada) using MRM. A turbo electrospray interface in positive ionization mode was used. Data processing was performed on Analyst 1.4.1 software package (SCIEX).

Detection

The mass transitions were selected as m/z (amu) 321.5→195.4 for NR, 325.4→195.4 for NRD4, respectively (Table-1).

Chromatographic conditions

Zorbax SB-C18, 4.6 x 75 mm, 3.5 μm 80 Å analytical column, mobile phase composition of 5 mM ammonium acetate in combination with methanol (30:70 v/v) with a flow-rate of 0.6 mL.min⁻¹. The column was placed at a temperature of 40°C. 20 μL of sample was injected into LC-MS/MS System. The analytes and Internal standards were eluted at 6.02 minutes (NR, NRD4) with total runtime of 13 minutes for each injection.

Calibration standards and quality control Samples

Standard Stock solutions of NR (100.0 μg/mL) were prepared in methanol. From each stock solution 500.0 ng/mL, 25.0 ng/mL, 2.5 ng/mL intermediate dilutions were prepared in plasma. Aliquots of 500.0 ng/mL, 25.0 ng/mL and 2.5 ng/mL were used to spike blank human plasma in order to obtain calibration curve standards of 10.0, 20.0, 200.0, 800.0, 1500.0, 3000.0, 4500.0, 6000.0, 7500.0 and 10000.0 pg/mL. Four levels of QC concentrations at 10.0, 30.0, 3500.0 and 8000.0 pg/mL (LLOQ, LQC, MQC and HQC) were prepared by using the different plasma. Spiked calibration curve standards and Quality control standards were stored at -30°C. Standard stock solution of NRD4 (100.0 μg/mL) were prepared in methanol. NRD4 was further diluted to 30.0 ng/mL (Spiked concentration of internal standard) using 50 % methanol and stored in the refrigerator 2-8 °C until analysis.

Sample preparation

Liquid-liquid extraction was carried out to extract the drug and IS for this purpose 100 μL of respective concentration of plasma sample was taken into polypropylene tubes and mixed with 50μL of internal standard (30.0 ng/mL). This was followed by addition of 100 μL of 10mM KH₂PO₄ solution and 2.5 mL of methyl tertiary butyl ether and vortexed for approximately 5 minutes. Then the Samples were centrifuged at 4000 rpm for 10 minutes at 20°C. Further, the supernatant was transferred into labeled polypropylene tubes and evaporated with nitrogen gas at 40°C. Then the samples were reconstituted with the reconstitution solution (5 mM ammonium acetate: methanol (30:70 v/v) and vortexed for 2 minutes. Finally, Sample was transferred into auto sampler vials to inject into the LC-MS/MS.

Selectivity and specificity

Selectivity was performed by analyzed the human blank plasma samples from six different sources (donors) with an additional hemolysed group and lipedimic group to test for interference at the retention times of analytes.

The peak area of NR in blank samples should not be more than 20% of mean peak area of LOQ of NR. Similarly, peak area of NRD4 in a blank sample should not be more than 5% of mean peak area of LOQ of NRD4.

Precision and accuracy

Precision and accuracy was determined by replicate analysis of quality control samples ($n = 6$) at LQC (low quality control), MQC (medium quality control) and HQC (high quality control) levels. The % CV should be less than 15%, and accuracy should be within 15% except LLOQ where it should be within 20%.

Matrix effect

The matrix effect due to plasma was used to evaluate the ion suppression/enhancement in a signal when comparing the absolute response of QC samples after pretreatment (Liquid-liquid extraction with diethyl ether) with that of the reconstituted samples. Experiments were performed at MQC levels in triplicate with six different plasma lots. The acceptable precision (%CV) of $\leq 15\%$ was maintained.

Recovery

The extraction efficiencies of NR and NRD4 were determined by analysis of six replicates at each quality control concentration level for NR and at one concentration for the internal standard NRD4. The percent recovery was evaluated by comparing the peak areas of extracted standards to the peak areas of non extracted standards (spiked into mobile phase).

Limit of detection and quantification (LOD and LOQ)

The limit of detection (LOD) is a parameter that provides the lowest concentration in a sample that can be detected from background noise but not quantitated. LOD was determined using the signal-to-noise ratio (S/N) of 3:1 by comparing test results from samples with known concentrations of analytes with blank samples.

The limit of quantitation (LOQ) is defined as the lowest concentration of analyte that can be determined with acceptable precision and accuracy. The LOQ was found by analyzing a set of mobile phase and plasma standards with a known concentration of NR.

Stability (Freeze- thaw, Auto sampler, Room temperature, Long term)

Stock solution stability: Stability in stock solution was performed by comparing the area response of analyte and internal standard in the stability sample, with the area response of sample prepared from fresh stock solution.

Stability studies in plasma: Stability in plasma samples were performed at the LQC and HQC concentration level using six replicates at each level. Analyte was considered stable if the % Change is less than 15% as per US-FDA guidelines^[17]. The stability of spiked human plasma samples stored at -30°C in autosampler (autosampler stability) was evaluated for 48 h. The stability of spiked human plasma samples stored at -30°C in autosampler (autosampler stability) was evaluated for 55.5 h. The autosampler sample stability was evaluated by comparing the extracted plasma samples that were injected immediately (time 0 h), with the samples that were reinjected after storing in the autosampler at 20°C for 55.5 h. The reinjection reproducibility was evaluated by comparing the extracted plasma samples that were injected immediately (time 0 h), with the samples that were re-injected after storing in the autosampler at 20°C for 27 h. The freeze-thaw stability was conducted by comparing the stability samples that had been frozen at -30°C and thawed three times, with freshly spiked quality control samples. Six aliquots each of LQC and HQC concentration levels were used for the freeze-thaw stability evaluation. For long term stability evaluation the concentrations obtained after 71 days were compared with initial concentrations.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Method development and validation

The goal of this work is to develop and validate a simple, rapid and sensitive assay method for the quantitative determination of NR from plasma samples. LC-MS/MS has been used as one of the most powerful analytical tools in clinical pharmacokinetics for its selectivity, sensitivity and reproducibility. The MS optimization was performed by direct infusion of solutions of NR and NRD4 into the ESI source of the mass spectrometer. The vital parameters like ionization type, temperature, voltage, gas parameters such as nebulizer and heater gases, compound parameters like DP, EP, FP, CE and CXP were optimized to obtain a better spray shape and ionization to form the respective productions from the protonated NR and NRD4 molecules (Figure. 2 & 3) (Table.1). Chromatographic conditions, especially, composition of the mobile phase, selection of suitable column was optimized through several trials to achieve the best resolution and increase the signal of analyte and internal standard. Different extraction methods like solid phase extraction, Liquid-liquid extraction, precipitation methods were optimized for extraction of NR and NRD4 from the plasma sample. A good separation and elution were achieved using 5 mM ammonium acetate: methanol (30:70 v/v) as the mobile phase, at a flow-rate of 0.6 mL/minutes and injection volume of 20 μL . Liquid-liquid extraction was chosen to optimize the drug and internal standard. The retention time was optimized 6.07 minutes for NR and NRD4 (Figure.2 & 3).

Linearity

Calibration curve was plotted as the peak area ratio (NR/NRD4) versus (NR) concentration. Calibration was found to be linear over the concentration range of 10.0 – 10000.0 pg/mL. The correlation coefficient (r^2) was greater than 0.9997 for all curves (Table 2).

Selectivity

The selectivity of the method assessed by comparing chromatograms of blank plasma. There were no significant endogenous peaks were observed at respective retention time of NR and NRD4. The results indicate that the method exhibited both good specificity and selectivity. (Fig.4& 5)

Precision and Accuracy

Precision and accuracy for this method were controlled by calculating the Within-run and Between-run variations at three concentrations (30.0, 3500.0 and 8000.0 pg/mL) of QC samples in six replicates. As shown in Table.3 the Within-run Precision and Accuracy were between 1.6 to 2.8 and 96.3 to 103.43.7% for. Similarly, the Between-run Precision and Accuracy were between 2.1 to 3.4 and 98.0 to 100.4%. These results indicate the adequate reliability and reproducibility of this method within the analytical range.

Matrix effect

The ion suppression/enhancement in the signal at MQC level was found %CV 1.30. These results indicating that there is no effect on ion suppression and ion enhancement.

Recovery

The extraction recoveries of NR were determined at three different concentrations 30.0, 3500.0 and 8000.0 pg/mL and 99.2 ±2.4, 94.2 ±1.7 and 96.9 ± 6.1% respectively. The overall average recovery was found to be 96.0 ± 2.8 and 98.76 ± 4.47. Recoveries of the analyte and IS were consistent, precise and reproducible.

Limits of Detection and Quantification (LOD&LOQ)

The LOQ signal-to-noise (S/N) values found for six injections of NR at LOQ concentration was 44.12.

Stability (Freeze - thaw, Auto sampler, Room temperature, Long term)

Stock solution stability was performed to check stability of NR and NRD4 in stock solutions prepared in methanol and stored at 2-8 °C in a refrigerator. The freshly prepared stock solutions were compared with stock solutions prepared before 26 days. The % change for NR and NRD4 were -0.02% and 0.03% indicate that stock solutions were stable at least for 26 days. Room temperature and autosampler stability was investigated at LQC and HQC levels. The results revealed that NR was stable in plasma for at least 72 h at room temperature, and 78 h in an auto sampler. It was confirmed that repeated freezing and thawing (three cycles) of plasma samples spiked with NR at LQC and HQC levels did not affect their stability. The long-term stability results also indicated that NR were stable in a matrix up to 71days at a storage temperature of -30°C. The results obtained from all these stability studies were tabulated in Table.4. Precision (%CV) is less than 5% for Room temperature, long-term, Freeze thaw, auto sampler stability.

Table.1: Optimized mass parameters of Niraparib and Niraparib -D4.

Molecular ion to production transitions used for quantification								
Compound	Molecular ion (m/z)				Product ion (m/z)			
Niraparib	868.12 [M+H] ⁺				321.54 ⁺			
Niraparib -D4	876.90 [M+H] ⁺				329.70 ⁺			
	Source dependent parameters (psi)				Compound dependent parameters (Volts)			
	CUR gas	CAD gas	Nebulizer gas	Heater gas	EP	DP	CE	CXP
Niraparib	20	4	20	40	10	30	35	12
Niraparib-D4	20	4	20	40	10	28	30	12
Common mass parameters for NR, NRD4								
Ion spray voltage	5500 volts							
Temperature	400°C							
Scan type	MRM							
Dwell time	500 msec							
Type of ionization	Electro spray ionization (ESI)							

Table 2: Calibration curve details of Niraparib.

Spiked plasma concentration (pg/mL)	Concentration measured(mean) (pg/mL) (n = 5)	Precision (CV %) (n = 5)
10.0	9.9±0.1	1.5
20.0	20.4±0.4	2.2
200.0	198.7±6.2	3.1
800.0	782.5±27.4	3.5
1500.0	1486.5±41.6	2.8
3000.0	2964.8±100.8	3.4
4500.0	4478.9±107.5	2.4
6000.0	5863.4±111.4	1.9
7500.0	7469.6±283.8	3.8
10000.0	9869.6±213.8	2.16

Table 3: Precision and accuracy (analysis with spiked plasma samples at three different concentrations).

Spiked plasma concentration (pg/mL)	Within-run (n=6)			Between-run (n=30)		
	Concentration measured (pg/mL) (mean ± S.D.)	Precision (CV %)	Accuracy %	Concentration measured (pg/mL) (mean ± S.D.)	Precision (CV %)	Accuracy %
300.0	28.9±0.5	1.6	96.3	29.4±0.7	2.4	98.0
3500.0	3426.7±95.9	2.8	97.9	3512.4±119.4	3.4	100.4
8000.0	7896.4±189.5	2.4	98.7	7945.6±166.9	2.1	99.3

Table 4: Stability of Niraparib in human plasma samples.

Stability experiments	Storage condition	Spiked plasma concentration (pg/ml)	Concentration measured (n=6) Mean ± SD	CV(%) (n=6)	Accuracy (%)
Bench top in plasma	RT	30	29.5±0.6	2.2	98.3
	72 hr	8000	7868.1±133.8	1.7	98.4
Processed (extracted sample)	Autosampler	30	29.2±0.8	2.6	97.3
	78 hr	8000	7937.7±150.8	1.9	99.2
Freeze/Thaw stability	-30°C	30	28.9±0.9	3.1	96.3
	Cycle-3	8000	7958.3±191.0	2.4	99.5
Long term stability in human plasma	-30°C 71 days	30	28.6±0.9	3.2	95.3
		8000	7896±213.2	2.7	98.7

Figure.1: Chemical structures of A) Niraparib B) Niraparib-D4.

Figure.2. Parent and product ion mass spectra (Q1& Q3) of Niraparib.

Figure.3. Parent ion and product ion mass spectra (Q1 & Q3) of Niraparib-D4.

Figure.4: Blank plasma chromatogram of interference free Niraparib and Niraparib -D4.

Figure.5: Chromatogram of LOQ sample (Niraparib and Niraparib -D4).

CONCLUSION

The proposed research work is highly specific due to the inherent selectivity of tandem mass spectrometry and has significant advantages over other described methods in previously. Quantification of Niraparib was compared with respective isotope labeled internal standard. Extraction of analyte and IS were achieved by using LLE. Linearity range, column, mobile phase, flow rate, injection volume, plasma usage volume for analysis was improved. The sensitivity of the assay is sufficient to follow accurately the pharmacokinetics of Niraparib. Hence this method has significant advantages over previously reported methods in-terms of Selectivity, sensitivity, Linearity, Reproducibility.

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